

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

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To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

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Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDÉLL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMÉLL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

Introductory.

After the strenuous research during the last twenty years of a number of distinguished investigators, it has now been proved that scurvy has to be looked upon as *one* disease in adults, young children and infants, in monkeys and guinea-pigs, with the same etiology, the same unknown pathogenesis, similar clinical symptoms and patho-anatomical changes, and identical therapeutics (MacCallum). Scurvy, however, is above all a disease of growth, and the most profitable studies have been made in quickly growing organisms, human infants or young monkeys and guinea-pigs. As surely as the quicker growth is a fundamental physiological factor, which principally distinguishes the undeveloped organism of the child from the developed organism of the adult and constitutes pediatrics as a special branch of medical science, as surely the scurvy problem is a central pediatric problem.

The plan which from the first I had drawn up for this work was the following. I wished 1) in connection with the study of the antiscorbutic substance of some Swedish wild berries¹ to examine the scorbutic changes which might be expected in liver, muscles and teeth, and to take up some scurvy problems for discussion; and 2) to study the mutual relations of scurvy and tuberculosis. As the result began to show clearer, I have widened the plan, and especially I have extended the patho-anatomical studies as far as the material available after the *post-mortem* examinations has allowed, in order by this means to support the new conception of the pathogenesis of scurvy, which presents itself as the final result of these studies. Many organs are left out, and among those lacking are the thyroid glands, the sexual organs, the hypophysis. Before long, I am going to publish complementary investigations, which have been carried on, but are not as yet brought into definitive form.

¹ With »strawberries» are in the following always meant wild wood-strawberries, *Fragaria vesca* L., and not *Fragaria moscata*.

Methods of experimental scurvy from Holst to the latest investigators.

In 1907, A. HOLST showed that a diet of cereal and water induces scurvy in young guinea-pigs, and together with T. FRÖLICH he then submitted different scurvy problems to a resultful examination, using guinea-pigs for the experiments. Their results having been confirmed from many quarters, the antiscorbutic substance (or group of substances) was ranged as vitamin C (DRUMMOND in 1919) among the vitamins (FUNK), or the accessory food factors (HOPKINS). Still the guinea-pig is the animal most frequently used for scurvy experiments. It is only the introduction of the monkey (HART and LESSING 1913) that has been a good addition, but through its quicker growth, easiness to handle, and cheapness, the guinea-pig has considerable advantages as experimental animal.

HOLST and FRÖLICH's basal diet, different kinds of cereal and water, is absolutely free from antiscorbutic factor. All the later investigators have confirmed the statement that the progress of scurvy in guinea-pigs on such a diet is very uniform. The nature and sequence of the symptoms may be studied in the works of HOLST and FRÖLICH (1907, 1912), COHEN and MENDEL (1918), HESS (1920). I give a short extract of their descriptions. After a symptom-less period of one or two weeks after the animals have been put on absolute diet, the first pathological sign appears, signalling the onset of the disorder. This first sign may vary, sometimes it is a loss of weight, sometimes a tenderness of joint or an inordinate excitability of the animal, which soon changes into inertness. After two or three weeks the animals show an unwillingness to move which has been ascribed to the swollen, tender joints, around which there are numerous hemorrhages, also in the musculature. Often they try to protect some specially affected joint by continually holding the corresponding limb lifted, »the scurvy position» of CHICK, HUME and SKELTON. The teeth become loosened and the incisors frequently break off. The coat is rough. Very often fractures occur at the

epiphyseal lines of the long tubular or medullated bones. The hemorrhagic diathesis may be extended to all tissues and after three, four or five weeks the animal succumbs, after having lost about a third of its weight at the beginning of the experiment. The results found at the *post-mortem* examination may be summarized thus: 1) Hemorrhages, most numerous and largest in and about the epiphyseal ends of the long bones; 2) Atrophy of the bone-system, presenting itself partly as a general osteoporosis, partly and principally as a typical disturbance of the growth zones of the long bones. Here the marrow loses its specific elements and gets to resemble a mucoid tissue («Gerüstmark» or frame-work marrow of SCHÖEDEL and NAUWERK). In the preparatory calcification zone the osteoblasts are lacking or have taken the appearance of spool-shaped cells of connective tissue. There is no trace to be seen of normal new bone. Infractures have often occurred, so that the bone-bridges lie scattered about in splinters — the «Trümmerfeld area». Besides fragments of bone there are also seen calcified cartilage bridges, recent and older hemorrhages and remains of such. In the cartilage the proliferating columns are in disorder. They are shorter, irregular, and the cartilage cells show degenerative changes in a higher degree than is normal. These changes often cause an enlargement of the epiphyseal line, which is specially evident in the costochondral junctions — a pronounced rosary.

If the animals that have scurvy get food containing antiscorbutic, the symptoms may be made to subside within a short time. It is easier still to get an estimation of the antiscorbutic value of an article of food, if from the beginning of the experiment a certain amount of it is given as an addition to the basal diet. The smallest quantity which then protects the animal from contracting scurvy, the *minimum protective dose*, is used as a relative standard of the antiscorbutic value of a substance. The smaller the minimum protective dose of a substance is found to be, the larger its antiscorbutic value.

In the experimental methods of Holst and Frölich, the

following investigators have proposed two modifications of principal importance.

1. The basal diet of the Norwegian authors lacks, besides antiscorbutic, also certain amino-acids, certain salts and vitamin A (McCOLLUM, SIMMONDS and PITZ). However, in order to ensure reliable conclusions it is necessary to give a diet which is insufficient only as to antiscorbutic. Such a diet is proposed from several quarters and it is obvious that it may be composed in various ways.

CHICK and HUME (1917) use the following: one part crushed oats and two parts of wheaten bran, and a daily ration of 50 to 60 ccm. of milk autoclaved for one hour at 120° C. According to HESS, this basal diet is so far unsatisfactory that it still retains a small amount of antiscorbutic vitamin.

SHERMAN, LA MER and CAMPBELL (1922) used the following diet:

oats, whole grain	59 %
skim milk powder	30 %
butter fat	10 %
sodium chloride	1 %

The skim milk powder was heated for two hours in open dishes with access of air. After such a treatment the milk has taken a yellow colour. Avoiding to let the milk get a burnt taste and observing the variations in C-vitamin contents of the milk during different seasons, every investigator must himself ascertain — say Sherman etc. — that his technique rids the milk of antiscorbutic.

LOPEZ-LOMA and RANDOIN in 1923 propose a basal diet of

white bean meal	84 %
granulated yeast	3 %
butter fat	4.5 %
calcium lactate	5 %
sodium chloride	1.5 %
paper filtrate	2 %

For preparing this food the meal is first boiled in water, and the other ingredients are then added. The authors mention that they do not use milk because it causes constipation in the animals.

These three basal diets represent the chief types that have been used. For my own part I have for practical reasons compounded a dietary in the following manner:

Crushed oats and wheaten bran *ad lib.*

60 ccm. lightly skimmed milk, bubbled through with air during 1 hour's boiling;

0,5 ccm. oleum jecoris Aselli, administered with a pipet.

The animals took this food readily until the last days of life. There remained but little of the administered quantities of oats, bran and milk. As in a few cases some animals showed an inclination for preferring oats to bran, I have in subsequent experiments, in order to be quite sure of a sufficient supply of B-vitamin, added 1 ccm. of a 50 % yeast emulsion, given with a pipet into the mouth of the animal as the cod-liver oil. — The importance of calculating the A-vitamin value of the food is evident after TOZER's investigation. Through the treatment which the milk in my diet has undergone, the A-vitamin is at least partially destroyed (HOPKINS, ZILVA, KORENCHEVSKY and CARR). The animals take the cod-liver oil readily. It had gradually become clear (HOLST and FRÖLICH, DELF, ANDERSON, DUTCHER etc., ELLIS etc.) that oxidization destroys the antiscorbutic more than heating, but that the most efficient and quickest destruction is reached by combining both. This may be done by adding hydrogen peroxide to the milk at a high temperature. That this treatment (buddization) of the milk causes scurvy in children fed entirely on such milk, has long been known to the specialists in pediatrics, at least in the North (MONRAD 1908, quoted by MEDIN). If this method is used, the hydrogen peroxide ought to be removed before feeding the animal. — Another method, used by me, is to let air be sucked through the milk during boiling. Already after half an hour of this treatment in an aëration bottle adapted for the purpose, the milk shows a light buff colour and gets a peculiar, boiled but

not burnt taste. ZILVA mentions that with this treatment the destruction of the antiscorbutic is almost complete, whereas SHERMAN etc. indicate it as being complete. According to a verbal statement of Zilva, Sherman's result is the correct one. This is also made evident from my control animals that have basal diet. As guinea-pigs in certain cases will stand milk-fat badly, I have given the milk lightly skimmed. In this manner I have not observed the inconveniences which Lopez-Loma and Randoin deem accompanying the use of milk in the basal diet.

2. The second alteration in Holst and Frölich's technique was also introduced by CHICK and HUME, and consists in using a carefully quantitative method. It can not be considered satisfactory only to place the foodstuff to be tried within the cage with the animals. On the contrary, it ought to be administered, in carefully measured rations, preferably with the aid of a pipet, directly into the animal's mouth. Only thus the guinea-pig experiment has become a biological method, comparable in accuracy to other biological methods (Hopkins).

For an examination of the antiscorbutic value of a substance to be unexceptionable, it is thus first of all necessary that the basal diet should be complete in all other respects than the antiscorbutic, and, secondly, that a quantitative procedure is adopted. Many investigations are still published (FABER 1920, HAWK etc. 1921, GIVENS etc. 1921, PEIPER 1923) where one or both of these conditions are not fulfilled. More often still the condition set forth by HESS and UNGER is neglected: a microscopic examination of the animals. Also this condition is indispensable. DELF and TOZER, who have shown that in guinea-pigs, with a diet in which only A-vitamin is lacking, certain changes appear in the epiphyses of the ribs, as a consequence forego the microscopic examination when testing the antiscorbutic value of different substances. This logic I cannot understand. The right conclusion of Delf and Tozer's investigation is, that it is necessary to attend to a fully sufficient supply of A-vitamin being present in the basal diet.

MOURIQUAND and MICHEL have published some experiments, which they consider to prove that cod-liver oil would

directly cause scurvy. They administered it in a dose of 2,5 ccm. to a basal diet of cereal and lemon juice. First of all is to be observed about this régime that it lacks certain minerals, specially calcium, as well as certain amino-acids. Furthermore, neither the changes found by the authors in the macroscopic, nor in the microscopic examination are such as to convince us that scurvy has been present. Finally, the dose of oil is so large that it may be suspected possibly to have occasioned alimentary disturbances. In sum, these investigations are ambiguous.

BEZSSONOFF reports that his experiments (1923) corroborate those now mentioned of Mouriquand and Michel about the injurious effect of cod-liver oil. The author's communications, however, do not in the least justify such an inference. The guinea-pigs in his series 9—12 do not seem to have had a sufficient ration of vitamin A, nor of vitamin C; but this can not be stated definitely as the animals do not seem to have been histologically examined. It may be mentioned that the temperature in Bezssonoff's laboratory went down below zero, which alone may have been enough to kill the animals. My series 33 and 35 show that Bezssonoff's conclusion as to the injurious influence on guinea-pigs of cod-liver oil in small dosage is not correct.¹

That the essential conditions, in spite of their necessity, are not yet universally observed, is probably due to the slow spreading of knowledge about the fundamental investigations. Still ten years ago, experiments on the influence of different salts on the bone formation (MASSLOW) could be made without a thought being given to the antiscorbutic in the food. In the same year (1913) such a distinguished investigator as WIELAND lacked knowledge of Holst's experiments. And still in 1923 papers on infantile scurvy are published (ROSENBUND) without considering the plainest inferences which may be drawn from the study of scurvy in guinea-pigs.

¹ MOURIQUAND and MICHEL in their latest report (1923) state, that the unfavourable influence of cod-liver oil is seen only when the dietary is incomplete regarding other constituents as certain salts and amino-acids.

Many authors (cf. RÆBIGER) point out that the guinea-pig as experimental animal is very delicate. It requires good care, is sensitive to changes in temperature, dietary a. s. o. In the basement of my villa in Hagalund, outside Stockholm, I have arranged a well lighted room, looking South, for housing the animals by installing hot water pipes and fixing 12 wooden cages by the wall opposite the window. The cages measured $45.5 \times 38.5 \times 36$ ccm. The whole front, which could be let down, consisted of a wire net with meshes 2.5 cm. square. In this way there was quite a uniform light on the animals. The bottom of the lowest cage was 0.5 meter above the floor. In the cages 1 to 8 animals were placed at the same time. From the point of view of infection it is advantageous to have as few animals as possible in each cage, preferably one or two. However, a comparison between my normal series and the others shows that the decisive factor for the infection generally seems to have been the lessened resistance caused by the scurvy. Cf. McCLENDON etc., who describe a pneumonia epidemic among their animals in spite of their having a cage each. My animals have been spared the great epidemics, cholera etc., which are described as not uncommon where a large number of guinea-pigs are kept.

The food basins were washed every day, sometimes every other day. The finest dry sawdust was used as litter on the tinplates covering the bottom of the cages and was as a rule changed every day, less often when pronounced oliguria was present.

As to the material, the animals were brought together from four different places, the difficulties of obtaining them all from one quarter being insurmountable at that time (July 1922 and March 1923). The animals were all of one breed, however, the so-called sleek or short-haired. Before the experiments began, the animals had full dietary from two to six weeks in order to make them recover after the transport and grow accustomed to their new surroundings, and especially learn to drink milk. In the records the animals have been drawn in their different colours. They were, as a rule, weighed every three days.

With regard to the suitable weight of the animals used for scurvy experiments, there are different opinions. COHEN and MENDEL use animals of 110—250 grams, HESS 200—300 grams, SHERMAN 300—350 grams, HOLST and FRÖLICH even bigger animals, up to more than 700 grams. It seems suitable that the weight should be between 200 and 500 grams. 174 of the present author's 189 animals had this weight at the beginning of the experiment, 14 weighed less than 200 grams, 1 more than 500.

With our deficient knowledge of the different need of antiscorbutic by the weight unit, which may be supposed to exist, a smaller animal probably wanting a larger quantity by the weight unit than a heavier one, I have thought it unsuitable to follow SHERMAN and SMITH in their calculating the dose of antiscorbutic to a uniform basis of body weight (300 grams), and I always indicate the absolute quantities directly given.

That the animals have thriven under the circumstances in question, is shown by the series 2 and 24, weight charts Fig. 96 and 118, 13 animals in all, which have had full dietary, composed of oats, bran, unboiled skim milk, swedes and green leaves, chiefly dandelion leaves. The increase in weight was satisfactory and the animals showed every sign of health till they were killed after 102—142 days. Two animals brought forth young, which in their turn developed normally. Only one animal died after 52 days; invalid after an acute tracheo-bronchitis, it was drowned in the milk basin. Neither this nor any of the other animals showed at the *post-mortem* examination and the subsequent histological examination the slightest sign of scurvy. The animals that were killed showed everywhere normal pictures. As controls with regard to scurvy the majority of the animals in series 3 and 25, in all 11, may also be regarded (concerning Cases 17 and 18, see below); these 11 animals, infected with a dose of tubercle bacilli, continued to increase in weight till they were killed after 102—142 days, without showing macro- or microscopical signs of scurvy. Likewise, the 16 animals in series 33 and 34 serve

as controls. Half their number lived till they were killed after 93 days, and none of them showed signs of scurvy, macro- or microscopically.

That the basal diet described above, and used by me, is free from antiscorbutic is shown by series 1 and 26, together comprising 16 animals, charts fig. 95 and 120. All these, with the exception of one who died on the first day of the experiment from an acute infection, developed typical scurvy and died after 18, 19, 24, 24, 24, 26, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 33, 33, 36 and 38 days respectively, with an average life-time of 28 days. SHERMAN states the average life time for animals of about 300 grams with totally scorbutic dietary to be 26—34 days, and other authors also indicate about 28 days. At the *post-mortem* examination of these guinea-pigs, all changes mentioned as typical for scurvy were present. The first scurvy symptom HESS has often been able to identify on the 12th—14th day. The earliest diagnosis was made by him on the 8th day. I have also seen CHICK's scurvy position intermediately appear on the 8th day, and in none of these cases the onset of the first symptoms was delayed longer than to the 16th day. From this I conclude that a demonstrable quantity of antiscorbutic has not been present in the basal diet. To believe, like ROBB etc. and HOWE, that the first symptom always presents itself on a fixed day and to interpret its coming a day or two later as proving the presence of antiscorbutic, is contrary to all results gained up till now. — As a careful microscopic examination of my animals has been carried out (see Records of cases), surely the basal diet fulfills the two fundamental claims, being quite free from antiscorbutic, and in all other respects a complete dietary.

The juices I have tried have been given to the animals with a pipet, graduated in 0,1 ccm. With patient handling the animals soon learn to eat in this manner, and soon they will suck the pipet as eagerly as a bottle-fed infant does his bottle, without losing a drop.

HESS has opposed the use of weight charts as scurvy charts. He admits that they often have a typical course,

when the animal only gets basal diet, with one rising and one sinking part (see Fig. 95 a. o.), but their course does not directly indicate the degree of the scurvy symptoms. Sometimes the scurvy symptoms will appear while the weight is still increasing, sometimes the weight goes down, when the animal refuses to eat or when an infection is at hand, continually from the beginning of the experiment. HESS has attempted to delineate a clinical curve. In practice, I have found this impossible. But I append the weight charts, as in any case they give much interesting information.

PART I.

The antiscorbutic value of some vegetable products.

Survey of experiments.

The *number* is found in the Records of cases p. 174.

Diet. B. diet = basal diet (see p. 12).

For the additions, see Discussion.

M. pr. d. = minimum protective dose of antiscorbutic (see p. 10).

Weight in grams at the beginning of the experiment and after death. The signs +, —, or ? after the final weight figure indicate that the animal was not weighed at the *post-mortem* examination and that towards the end the weight curve was pronouncedly rising (+), falling (—), or level (?).

Scurvy. For the definitions, see pp. 35.

Scorbut manifestus gravior ****.

» » mitior ***.

» latens gravior (****).

» » extensus **.

» » levior and incipiens *.

Table 1.

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Life-time days	Remarks
			initial	final			
I	1	Basal diet. 0.0 m. pr. d.	250	190	****	24	
	2		270	190	****	26	
	3		270	215	****	38	
	4		260	180	****	31	
	5		295	195	****	33	
	6		275	170	****	27	
	7		270	160	****	26	
	8		275	200	****	24	
II	9		280	600	0	142	Chloro- formed
	10		210	750	0	142	» , gravid
	11		270	635	0	142	» , I-para
	12		100	710	0	94	»
III	13	B. diet with swedes and green leaves. > 1 m. pr. d.	295	730	0	142	»
	14		300	710	0	142	» , I-para
	15		320	700+	0	142	» (twins)
	16		325	580	*	142	»
	17		330	780	0	142	»
	18		345	560?	**	142	»
	19		365	755+	0	142	»
IV	20	B. diet + 1 cem. red whortleberry juice, 1 year old, bought at grocer's. 0.0 m. pr. d.	295	170	****	28	
	21		300	200	****	26	
	22		280	180	****	28	
	23		295	195	****	30	
V	24	B. diet + 5 cem. of the same juice. 0.0 m. pr. d.	280	145	****	28	
	25		235	210-	****	28	
	26		290	200	****	29	
	27		285	170	****	27	
VI	28	B. diet + 10 cem. of the same juice. 0.0 m. pr. d.	270	175	****	32	
	29		235	240	(****)	12	Died of pneumonia ac.
	30		200	140	(****)	14	Died of septicemia

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Life-time days	Remarks	
			initial	final				
VI	31		295	185	****	30		
	32		355	250	****	31		
	33		525	320	****	32		
VII	34	B. diet + 5 ccm. of raw fresh red whortleberry juice 1922. 0.0 m. pr. d.	430	210	****	38		
	35		400	255	****	35		
	36		450	240	****	43		
	37		440	250	****	31		
VIII	38	B. diet + 2 ccm. red whortleberry juice, pressed 1922 from berries pre- served in water since 1921. 0.0 m. pr. d.	250	220—	(****)	8	Died of enteritis ac.	
	39		265	140	****	27		
	40		270	170	****	28		
	41		275	220—	****	37		
IX	42	B. diet + 7 ccm. of the same juice. 0.0 m. pr. d.	230	175	****	29		
	43		300	180	****	25		
	44		345	220	****	26		
	45		290	205	****	30		
X	46	B. diet + 5 ccm. juice pressed 1922 from berries, stir- red with sugar 1921 0.0 m. pr. d.	300	205	****	23	Died of septicemia	
	47		210	175—	****	34		
	48		235	170	****	22		Suffocation
	49		270	190	****	26		
XI	50	B. diet + 1 ccm. raw juice of fresh blue whortleber- ries 1922. 0.0 m. pr. d.	180	155	****	30		
	51		230	150	****	29		
	52		230	155	****	29		
	53		250	180	****	28		
XII	54	B. diet + 5 ccm. of the same juice. 0.0 m. pr. d.	240	140	****	19	Died of suffocation	
	55		240	175	****	35		
	56		275	185	****	32		
	57		230	170	****	23		

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Life-time days	Remarks
			initial	final			
XIII	58	B. diet + 5 ccm. juice from stewed blue whortleberries 1921. 0.1 m. pr. d.	210	135	***	60	In dying condition killed with ether
	59		275	215—	***	52	
	60		255	195	***	39	
	61		255	200	***	57	
XIV	62	B. diet + 10 ccm. of the same juice. 0.2 m. pr. d.	255	230	*	10	Died through overlying
	63		260	150	**	29	Died with lymphadenit. supp.
	64		255	245	*	4	Died with lymphadenit. supp.
	65		315	215	***	61	
	66		405	340	***	32	Died of bronchopneumonia ac.
XV	67	B. diet + 5 ccm. juice of fresh strawberries stirred with sugar. 0.1 m. pr. d.	240	160	***	42	
	68		280	180	***	46	
	69		255	160	***	50	
	70		285	250	***	55	
XVI	71	B. diet + 5 ccm. fir needle decoction. 0.0 m. pr. d.	370	210	****	29	
	72		380	240	****	29	
	73		445	250	****	28	
	74		360	250	****	27	
XVII	75	B. diet + 1 ccm. fresh orange juice, yet ²⁰ / ₁₀ — ¹⁸ / ₁₁ other juice. Varied value of m. pr. d.	410	260	***	46	
	76		395	390+	Healing	66	Chloroformed
	77		345	435+	"	66	"
	78		320	360+	"	66	"
XVIII	79	B. diet without ol. jec. Aselli + 2 ccm. fresh orange juice.	335	390	*	30	Died of peritonitis ac.
	80		265	260	*	19	Died of pneumonia ac.
	81	B. diet without ol. jec. Aselli + 4 ccm. fresh orange juice.	420	400—	0	60	Chloroformed
	82		480	510—	0	60	"
XIX	83	B. diet + 3 ccm. fresh tomato juice 1922. 0.1 m. pr. d.	340	200	***	43	
	84		400	280	***	39	
	85		270	230	***	39	
	86		305	225	***	43	Died through drowning

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Life-time days	Remarks
			initial	final			
XX	87	Oats and bran, 200 ccm. milk, raw and fresh, for them all together. 0.1 m. pr. d.	320	260	***	37	Lymphadenitis supp.
	88		345	220	***	59	
	89		340	200	***	37	
	90		350	220	***	46	
XXI	91	B. diet + 2 ccm. raspberry juice, preserved. 0.0 m. pr. d.	365	235	****	28	
	92		280	200	****	27	
XXII	93	B. diet + 2 ccm. black currant juice, preserved. 0.0 m. pr. d.	410	220	****	37	Cause of death doubtful
	94		250	220	(****)	6	
XXIII	95	B. diet + swedes and green leaves > 1 of m. pr. d.	240	270	0	9	Died at the first pipet feeding
	96		200	220	0	8	» » » » »

Summary and discussion.

Red whortleberries (*Vaccinium vitis idæa*, L.). Of the antiscorbutic value of these berries there is only one investigation in the literature, by FÜRST. Seven guinea-pigs were given a basal diet of oats, yellow peas and rice meal, and with this diet in all 100 ccm. red whortleberry juice (l. c. p. 148; on p. 128 the quantity of juice for each animal is indicated as 25 ccm.). The animals died after 18—28 days and all showed scurvy in a higher or lower degree. We are not told whether all the juice was consumed, and in any case it is impossible to know how much the different animals have had. Fürst believes he can conclude a certain protective effect. The conclusion is doubtful.

29 of my animals have been used for testing red whortleberries. So-called natural juice, bought at a grocer's and for the composition of which there has been no guarantee, has been tested in doses of 1, 5 and 10 ccm. Further the juice

of raw berries bought in the market-place was tested in a dose of 5 cm.; the juice of whortleberries, which juice since 1921 had been kept in closed bottles with water poured over them, in doses of 2 and 7 cm.; and the juice of crushed whortleberries, prepared in 1921 by stirring raw berries together with the same quantity of sugar during an hour. All the 29 animals showed manifest signs of scurvy; six, who died of intercurrent infection, less pronounced, the rest very marked, and died, counted in groups (the six animals mentioned are left out), after 28, 28, 31, 37, 31, 28 and 34 days, respectively. The group that had got the juice of fresh, raw berries, lived longest, which might be supposed to be due to a certain amount of antiscorbutic; but the lifetime, 37 days, is too short to allow any such conclusion.

Thus, I have not been able to prove the presence of an antiscorbutic substance in red whortleberry juice prepared in different ways. This does not preclude the possibility that a small amount may exist and under certain circumstances be demonstrated. PARSONS pointed out in 1920 that the guinea-pig, who requires a comparatively large dose of antiscorbutic, is not a very suitable animal for testing food-stuffs of low antiscorbutic value. It may be mentioned that the peasants are said of old to have regarded the red whortleberries as possessing a certain antiscorbutic value.

Blue whortleberries (*Vaccinium myrtillus*). Not tested earlier.

First fresh, raw juice of the year 1922 was tested in doses of 1 and 5 cm., then juice of berries from 1921, which had been boiled and stirred for half an hour in an open pan, and afterwards kept in a closed bottle for a year, in doses of 5 and 10 cm. *The raw juice of 1922 showed no protective effect whatever.* The animals in both series died after 29 and 27 days, respectively, in pronounced scurvy. *The boiled juice of 1921, on the other hand, showed a certain protective effect, which for the doses given — 5 and 10 cm. — corresponded to 0.1—0.2 of the minimum protective dose.* An animal from

the first group, that had 5 ccm., died of intercurrent infection after 39 days without showing the highest degree of scurvy; the other three died of severe scurvy after an average lifetime of 56 days. Of the five animals who had 10 ccm., 4 died of infections, two very soon, two after 29 and 32 days with slight scurvy symptoms. The fifth died with pronounced scurvy after 61 days. This juice of 1921 had undergone a treatment which must be supposed to have reduced its antiscorbutic value in a high degree. As it nevertheless had proved itself so far valuable, *these whortleberries of 1921, when fresh, must have possessed quite a high antiscorbutic value.*

Strawberries. Not tested earlier.

The juice of fresh berries was given for three weeks, and subsequently the juice of berries which at the end of August had been stirred with like quantity of sugar during half an hour and then kept in a closed jar a month. *The strawberry juice showed a certain protective effect, in a dose of 5 ccm. corresponding to about 0.1 of the minimum protective dose.* One animal died with less highly marked scurvy after 42 days, the three others with pronounced scurvy after an average of 50 days.

Decoction of fir needles.

Not earlier tested experimentally on animals. The army-surgeon of Charles XII, ERBENIUS, is said to have cured »soldier epidemics» with it. TOBLER states, without indicating his dose, that he has cured scurvy in children by this means; the same thing is reported by UMBER, whereas FINKELSTEIN mentions that he has seen no clinical effect; perhaps, he adds, because the needles were not sufficiently fresh.

I tried a decoction of fir needles, prepared in the following way. The tops of fir sprigs were picked in July 1922 and kept in a cellar for six weeks; 0.5 kg. was soaked for an hour in 2 litres of water nearly 100° C. Then the decoction was strained off and bottled. *5 ccm. of this decoction showed no antiscorbutic effect whatever in four animals.* They died after

28 days. For the present it is impossible to decide whether this depended on the scanty sunshine in 1922, of which more below, or on the needles not being fresh, as Finkelstein suggests for his cases, or perhaps picked too late in the year, or whether the dose was too weak to show any effect in the guinea-pigs.

Tomatoes.

The juice of tomatoes, both fresh and sterilized, is by common consent stated to be highly antiscorbutic. A daily dose of 3 ccm. will protect a guinea-pig from scurvy. It has been proved that fully ripe red tomatoes have greater antiscorbutic value than those which are unripe and green. For my tests I used tomatoes, that had ripened late in the season of 1922. They were fully ripe but not so intensely red in colour as tomatoes may become. The juice was pressed out and was given immediately in a dose of 3 ccm. to each animal. The animals died in the most severe scurvy after an average of 41 days, which possibly may be counted as proving *a certain antiscorbutic value, but in any case very slight* (ca. 0.1 min. protective dose). In the literature I have only found one statement of failing clinical antiscorbutic effect of ripe tomatoes, and that by FINKELSTEIN.

Milk.

200 ccm. of fresh raw milk were given during October and November 1922 to four animals, who consumed it jointly; they may have drunk different quantities. They died after 37, 37, 46 and 59 days, with pronounced scurvy. 1 litre of this milk at the least can be reckoned necessary to protect these four animals. This agrees with the experience of different investigators that milk, in itself a weak antiscorbutic, is especially weak when the cows are kept in the shed (DUTCHER etc., HESS, UNGER and SUPPLEE, BARNES and HUME, HART). The essentially different lifetime of the animals also emphasizes the necessity stated by CHICK and HUME of a quantitative dosage for each animal of the substance to be tested.

Raspberry juice.

According to HOLST and FRÖLICH 10 ccm. of raspberry juice, boiled as well as raw, have a complete protective effect. I found no protective effect whatever in a liquid, bought at a pharmaceutical chemist's as »raspberry juice 1922» and given to two animals in a dose of 5 ccm.

Black currant juice.

Bought and tested under the same circumstances as the preceding, it showed no protective effect.

No conclusions must be drawn from these last experiments about the antiscorbutic value of the berries, no more than from the series with »natural» red whortleberry juice from a grocer's. But they show that it is very unsafe to rely upon berry juices and syrups bought in shops as antiscorbutic.

Orange juice.

According to various experiments (HESS), guinea-pigs require 3 ccm. of fresh raw juice to protect them completely from scurvy, while 1.5 ccm. is enough to prevent the manifestation of clinical signs (Davey).

I gave 2 ccm. and 4 ccm. of fresh raw juice and stated for the latter dose complete protection. (Series 18.) Series 17 is interesting. First the animals had 1 ccm. of raw fresh orange juice. This was pressed out of oranges that looked dry and gave but little juice; it was in October and the season was drawing to its close. The weight charts of the four animals were already declining when the oranges disappeared from the market, and therefore the animals had a dose of preserved orange juice. As this has been prepared through stirring in an open pan for nearly an hour and the antiscorbutic in the juice might thus be supposed to have lost its potency, the preserved juice was given in a dose (8 ccm.), twice as large as the one calculated to be equivalent to 1 ccm. of fresh juice. Nevertheless the animals lost weight very quickly and got worse and worse. When, after 20 days of this preserved juice, new fresh oranges were again to be had, in the month of December, 1 ccm. of fresh juice was again administered.

No. 75, who was then extremely feeble, died the next day. At first, one of the other three also showed a somewhat continued sinking of the weight curve, which is described as typical for the first days of the healing stage. Then they all rapidly recovered and grew quite lively. This series proves that even oranges may vary in their antiscorbutic value, which has been earlier pointed out incidentally by DELF, but does not seem to be universally recognized (STILL 1920).

What is most remarkable in these results, is the slight antiscorbutic power of the vegetable products of 1922. In raw blue whortleberries from this year there was no antiscorbutic value to be found, whereas it was fairly high in berries from 1921. Tomatoes, which may generally be compared to oranges, contained in the late autumn of 1922 hardly any antiscorbutic.

Raspberry juice and decoction of fir needles from the same year did not show any antiscorbutic potency either, but this may perhaps be due to special circumstances.

The reason for this marked poverty of the antiscorbutic factor in the products of 1922 can not with certainty be stated. As it has been proved that the degree of ripeness is of importance for the C-vitamin contents, and as fruits and berries ripen under the influence of the sun, it seems natural to connect the antiscorbutic potency with the sun radiance. FUNK suggests in 1922: »This original contents (of antiscorbutic) may vary with the country, in which it is produced, with the condition of the soil, the climate and so on», but the sun radiance as important factor for the forming of antiscorbutic has neither been presumed by him nor by any one else. As to the A-vitamin, it has been proved only to be formed in the light (STEENBOCK, COWARD).

If we inquire into the time of sun radiance during the late summer of 1922 in Stockholm (all the products used for the research were from the neighbourhood of Stockholm), we find it to have been as follows.¹

¹ The figures have been kindly communicated by the meteorologist at the Public Meteorological Institution, Knut Haldin.

Table 2.

	Hours of sunshine per month:		Average 1908—1920
	1921	1922	
July	310	257	266
August	239	192	200
September	210	149	160

From this table we see, that whereas the figures for the time of sunshine in July, August and September 1921 were 16.6, 19.5 and 31.2 per cent., respectively, *above* the average, they were for the same months in 1922 3.3, 4, and 6.9 per cent. *below* the average. In 1921, Stockholm had an unusually sunny late summer, in 1922 it was unusually cloudy. The hypothesis about the difference in time of sunshine causing the varying antiscorbutic potency of berries, fruits and leaves, agrees well with these facts.

Conclusions.

With regard to the antiscorbutic value of the examined products, the investigation has thus shown that

- 1) strawberries (1922) and blue whortleberries (1921) had a certain antiscorbutic value, whereas blue whortleberries (1922) were without any demonstrable antiscorbutic potency;
- 2) antiscorbutic could not be detected in red whortleberries 1922, nor in decoction of fir needles of that year;
- 3) fully ripened, though late, tomatoes of less intensely red colour held, in 1922, but little antiscorbutic;
- 4) these changes in antiscorbutic value may be explained as due to different sunlight time during the ripening in different years;
- 5) ripe oranges vary in antiscorbutic value according to the different quality of the fruit.

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